

A Pilot Study on the Use of Artificial Intelligence for Detecting Parkinson’s Disease Through Speech Analysis

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Keywords: Parkinson’s disease, Speech analysis, Acoustic features, Machine learning.

Abstract

Parkinson’s disease (PD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder producing motor and non-motor impairments. Clinical diagnosis continues to depend on specialist neurological assessment and structured diagnostic criteria, which may delay detection and limit access in resource-constrained settings [1]. Computational speech analysis has therefore attracted increasing interest as a non-invasive and objective screening approach, commonly implemented using acoustic analysis tools such as PRAAT [2]. Among early non-motor signs, voice and speech changes are consistently reported and can serve as objective biomarkers for screening and monitoring [3, 4].

This pilot study develops and evaluates an automated, non-invasive pipeline that screens for PD from brief sustained-vowel recordings using PRAAT with Python (Parsemouth) for reproducible acoustic feature extraction [2]. Features known to reflect dysphonia and phonatory instability, including local jitter, local shimmer, Harmonics-to-Noise Ratio (HNR), and mean period pulse (MPP), were extracted, as these measures have been previously linked to PD-related vocal impairment [3, 4]. Extraction settings, data quality checks, and normalization steps were standardized to improve cross-dataset comparability. Five supervised classifiers were trained and compared, including Support Vector Machine (SVM), Gradient Boosting, Random Forest (RF), XGBoost, and LightGBM [5, 6, 7, 8, 9]. To avoid within-subject leakage and produce conservative, deployment-oriented estimates, all evaluations used Leave-One-Subject-Out (LOSO) cross-validation, reporting subject-wise metrics across folds. Experiments used three datasets to assess robustness and cross-population generalization, consisting of a commonly used public Parkinson’s voice dataset [3], an external Turkish dataset publicly available via Figshare [10], and a locally collected Thai volunteer dataset.

Ensemble tree models consistently outperformed linear baselines. The Random Forest classifier achieved the best trade-off between sensitivity and specificity on the internal dataset (aggregate F1 ≈ 0.87 under LOSO), with XGBoost and LightGBM producing competitive results. Performance on the external Turkish dataset and the smaller Thai sample remained acceptable but showed modest

degradation, consistent with recording-condition heterogeneity and limited local sample size. Per-fold confusion matrices and ROC and Precision-Recall analyses further characterize classifier decision trade-offs.

This study contributes a demonstration of a low-cost, reproducible speech-based screening pipeline suitable for resource-limited settings, emphasizes subject-wise (LOSO) validation to avoid optimistic estimation, and provides processing scripts and model recipes to support replication and translation. Limitations include modest local sample size and focus on sustained vowels rather than connected speech. Future work should expand multi-site data collection, include connected speech, and evaluate clinician-facing interfaces. A combined workflow and performance figure is provided in the manuscript to aid interpretation.

Acknowledgments

This research was conducted under the guidance of Dr. Thanate Angsuwattanakul at the College of Biomedical Engineering, Rangsit University. The authors gratefully acknowledge the College of Biomedical Engineering, Rangsit University, for providing academic support, computational resources, and research facilities. We also thank the contributors of the publicly available Parkinson’s disease speech datasets used in this study, as well as all volunteers who participated in the data collection process.

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Figure 1: The ROC curves of the trained models using a combination of the internal and external datasets under the LOSO cross-validation scheme.